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LEGAL STATUS OF THE NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC, WHICH IS AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

In 2024, it will be 100 years since Nakhchivan, which is an integral part of the Republic of Azerbaijan, was established as an autonomous republic. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev dated December 30, 2023, taking into account that the establishment of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is a very important event in the political history of Azerbaijan, the 100th anniversary of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic will be widely celebrated.

This article discusses the organization and legal status of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan, Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, autonomy, legal status, constitution, Constitution of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

1. Introduction

The autonomy of Nakhchivan arose out of historical necessity. Thus, the occurrence of very complex historical conditions in the region in 1918-20, the separation of Nakhchivan land from Azerbaijan as a result of the loss of Zangezur, emboldened the Armenians, who had been wishing to own this land with the help of their foreign patrons for many years. However, the attempt to join Nakhchivan to Armenia was met with strong opposition from the local population. In January 1921, a referendum was held in Nakhchivan on its inclusion in the Azerbaijan SSR, as a result of the opinion poll, 90 percent of the population supported Nakhchivan region remaining in the Azerbaijan SSR [3, p.342].

2. Basics of the legal status of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

The autonomous status of Nakhchivan was first reflected in the Moscow Treaty dated March 16, 1921. According to Article 3 of that agreement, Nakhchivan province is organized as an autonomous territory under the auspices of Azerbaijan, with the condition that Azerbaijan will never compromise this protectorate to a third state [2, p.26]. A similar provision was established in Article 5 of the Kars Agreement dated October 13, 1921 [2, p. 70]. The Moscow and Kars agreements became the guarantor of the future existence and development of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic as an international legal act. The subsequent constitutional acts of the USSR, Azerbaijan SSR and Nakhchivan MSSR took these international agreements as a basis. This was reflected in the November 1922 decision of the Political Bureau of the Central Committee of the Russian Communist (Bolshevik) Party "On the establishment of the autonomous Nakhchivan region within the Azerbaijan SSR" and was recognized in the special decision of the First Transcaucasian Congress of Soviets dated December 12, 1922. [4, p. 14].

Nakhchivan SSR, announced on March 16, 1921, was transformed into Nakhchivan region within Azerbaijan by the decision of the Central Executive Committee of Azerbaijan dated June 16, 1923. By the decision of the Central Executive Committee of Azerbaijan

dated February 9, 1924, Nakhchivan Autonomous Region was reorganized as an autonomous republic [4, p.16].

The issues related to the status of Nakhchivan were reflected in the 1927, 1937 and 1978 constitutions of the Azerbaijan SSR.

Chapter VIII of the first national Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, adopted in 1995, is entirely dedicated to the status of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Provisions on the legal status of autonomy, the structure and powers of its higher bodies are reflected here. Article 134 of the Constitution states that the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is an autonomous state within the Republic of Azerbaijan. The status of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is determined by this Constitution, and the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is an integral part of the Republic of Azerbaijan [6].

The autonomy of Nakhchivan does not harm the unitary state structure of the Republic of Azerbaijan. First, the autonomy of Nakhchivan is a territorial autonomy, and this status results from the lack of direct land connection with the main territory of Azerbaijan. Secondly, when the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic was being prepared, the main features related to the fundamentals of the constitutional structure of the Republic of Azerbaijan - political rights and freedoms, a unified judicial system, unified bases of legislation, a unified state language and state symbols, unified citizenship, unified armed forces, unified national currency and finance - the application of the credit system was taken into account [4, p.27].

All this is reflected in the Constitution by guaranteeing the sovereignty of the Republic of Azerbaijan as a unitary state and a subject of international law. The unity of Azerbaijan's statehood is established both by the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan states that normative legal acts have direct legal force in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. According to Article 134 of the Constitution, the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, laws, decrees of the President of

the Republic of Azerbaijan and decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan are binding on the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The Constitution and laws of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic adopted by the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic should not conflict with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan, and the decisions adopted by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic should not conflict with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the decrees of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, and the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is presented to the Milli Majlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan and approved by the Constitutional Law [6]. Constitutional laws are an integral part of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, and the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, like the Constitutional Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan, has superior legal force in the legislative system of the country.

The adoption of the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan became a historical necessity. For this purpose, by the decision of the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic dated December 23, 1995 No. 16-1, a commission was established to prepare the draft of the new Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The commission prepared the draft of the new Constitution and submitted it to the commission preparing the draft of the new Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The project was discussed here 4 times, passed the expertise of the Council of Europe, the Venice Commission and the European Commission. The final version of the project was sent to the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic for discussion with the letter of President Heydar Aliyev No. 1-248 dated April 12, 1998, the chairman of the commission that prepared the draft of the new Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan [5, p.1]. The project was adopted by the Supreme Assembly on April 28, 1998, approved by the Milli Majlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan on December 29, 1998 and entered into force. The Constitution consists of 6 chapters, 50 articles and transitional provisions.

The Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, which is organically connected with the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, protects the independence, sovereignty and territorial integrity of the Azerbaijan state, ensures a decent standard of living of the people of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic based on justice and the law, improves their livelihood, democratic, legal, it was adopted with noble intentions, such as providing security for the secular state structure and protecting the rule of law.

According to Article 1 of the Constitution of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, Nakhchivan Autonomous State is a democratic, legal, secular autonomous republic within the Republic of Azerbaijan and its status is determined by the Constitution of the Republic of

Azerbaijan, Moscow dated March 16, 1921 and Kars international treaties dated October 13, 1921 [7].

According to Article 1 of the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the Nakhchivan Autonomous State is a democratic, legal, secular autonomous republic within the Republic of Azerbaijan, and its status is determined by the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Moscow International Agreements of March 16, 1921, and the Kars International Agreements of October 13, 1921. is done [7].

The state authorities of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are organically connected with each other and work harmoniously. According to the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is independent in solving the issues related to its powers by the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan. All other issues related to the interests of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are resolved by the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, provided that the resolution of these issues is not attributed to the powers of the state bodies of the Republic of Azerbaijan. It is related to the general interests of the Republic of Azerbaijan in solving issues related to the powers of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

3. Supreme authorities of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

Article 3 of the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic establishes the principle of separation of powers, which is one of the most important attributes of democracy and the legal state. Legislative power in the autonomous republic is exercised by the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, executive power by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, and judicial power by the courts of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic [7].

3.1. Supreme Assembly (Ali Majlis) of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

The Supreme Assembly (Ali Majlis) of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is the supreme representative body that expresses the sovereign will of the citizens. The Supreme Assembly consists of 45 deputies and they are elected by free, personal and secret voting based on the majoritarian electoral system, general, equal and direct suffrage. Every citizen of the Republic of Azerbaijan, who lives permanently in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and has the right to participate in elections, can be elected a deputy of the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in accordance with the law. The Supreme Assembly is authorized when the powers of 31 deputies are confirmed.

Article 24 of the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic contains the general rules established by the Supreme Assembly, and article 25 contains the issues resolved [7]. Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic Elections to the Supreme Assembly, the status of Supreme Assembly deputies and the commissioner for human rights, taxes in accordance with the economic and tax policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the directions of the autonomous

republic's economy, social security, environmental protection, tourism, health, science and culture, as well as establishes general rules and adopts laws on other issues related to its authority by the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

In addition, the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, laws on the organization of the work of the Supreme Assembly and approval of the budget of the autonomous republic, approval of economic and social programs of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, appointment and dismissal of the Prime Minister, approval of the composition of the Cabinet of Ministers, trust in the Cabinet of Ministers, higher election of the Commissioner for Human Rights of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic with the presentation of the official, appointment of the members of the Central Election Commission of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic with the proposal of the top official, approval of the decrees of the top official in the cases provided for in the Constitution, as well as other matters attributed to his authority by the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan makes decisions on issues.

The Supreme official of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is the chairman of the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic lists the powers of both the chairman of the Supreme Assembly and the Supreme official. The position of the chairman of the Supreme Assembly is the main position, and the position of the Supreme official is a derivative position. If the powers of the chairman of the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are mainly related to the organization of the work of the Supreme Assembly, The Supreme official exercises broad powers both in the legislative and executive spheres.

3.2. Cabinet of Ministers of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

According to Article 34 of the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the executive power in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is exercised by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, and it is the upper executive body of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic [7]. The Cabinet of Ministers of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is subordinate to the Supreme Assembly and reports regularly to it. The Cabinet of Ministers of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic includes the Prime Minister of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, his deputies, ministers and heads of other central executive authorities. As mentioned above, the composition of the Cabinet of Ministers is approved by the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic on the proposal of the Prime Minister of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic prepares the draft budget of the autonomous republic and submits it to the Supreme Assembly of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and executes the budget of the autonomous republic, ensures the implementation of the economic and social

programs of the autonomous republic, leads the ministries and other central executive authorities, cancels their acts, It resolves other issues related to its powers by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan and represents the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan in economic and cultural spheres.

3.3. Supreme Court of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

In the Autonomous Republic of Nakhchivan, judicial power is exercised only by courts. The Supreme Court of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic administers justice on appeal in the territory of the autonomous republic. However, unlike other appellate courts in the country, the Supreme Court of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is also a constitutional control body. The Supreme Court, upon request, verifies the compatibility of legal acts with lower force in the hierarchy with legal acts of higher force. In addition, anyone can complain to the Supreme Court of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic about the normative legal acts of the legislative and executive authorities of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, as well as municipal and court acts that violate his rights and freedoms, in order to restore the violated human rights and freedoms in accordance with the law.

In addition to the Supreme Court of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, district and city courts as general courts, and Grave Crimes, Military, Administrative and Commercial courts of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic as specialized courts exercise judicial power.

There are no political issues under the jurisdiction of the supreme authorities of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. That is, the authorities of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic cannot solve any issue of a political nature. This also means that the determination of mutual relations between the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and the Republic of Azerbaijan is carried out unilaterally by the Republic of Azerbaijan. Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic does not participate in defining these relations. This is natural, because the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is an integral part of the Republic of Azerbaijan and subordinate to it [1, p.481].

4. Plenipotentiary representation of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic

One of the main innovations in the political history of Nakhchivan and Azerbaijan as a whole was the establishment of the Institute of Plenipotentiary representation of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan No. 1917 dated December 22, 2022, the said institute was established and its Statute was approved. To coordinate the activities of local executive authorities operating in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and exercise control over their activities, to ensure the interaction of local executive authorities with other state bodies (institutions) in order to ensure the sustainable socio-economic development of the Autonomous Republic, to

ensure the public, providing regular reports to the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the social and economic situation and acting in other directions determined by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan are the main activities of the plenipotentiary [8].

The Plenipotentiary representation of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is headed by the plenipotentiary representative of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, appointed and dismissed by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan and directly subordinate to the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Plenipotentiary representative is an official representing the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and exercises the powers established by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

5. Conclusion

The reflection of the constitutional status of Nakhchivan autonomy in the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the elaboration of the details of this status in the Constitution of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic created a solid foundation for the constitutional structure of Azerbaijan, allowed the creation of harmonious relations between the state bodies of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, and the creation of a scientifically based public administration system.

The creation of the institution of the Plenipotentiary representation of the President of Azerbaijan in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and the appointment of the Plenipotentiary representative ensure the harmony of the unitary state administration of Azerbaijan and the status of the autonomous republic of Nakhchivan. Thus, the appointment of the Plenipotentiary representative of the President has led to increasing the efficiency of the management method in Nakhchivan, further development of the region's economy, successful implementation of reforms, and accelerated the process of attracting local and foreign investors to the autonomous republic.

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